

Propositions

1. ‘Geroprotective’ bacterial genes increase with age while associating with lower frailty, indicating their potential role in promoting healthy ageing (this thesis).
2. HIV infection serves as a unique model for studying accelerated ageing and immune dysfunction (this thesis).
3. Ageing and HIV infection can create a ‘double hit’ effect on the gut microbial community (this thesis).
4. Bacterial strain-level analysis is essential for understanding the diverse functional impacts of the same bacterial species (this thesis).
5. Bacterial tryptophan metabolism represents a key pathway connecting gut dysbiosis to chronic inflammation during HIV infection (this thesis).
6. Multi-omics approaches are essential to uncover the functional significance of microbial variations in human health and disease.
7. “The mystery of life isn’t a problem to solve, but a reality to experience.” – *Reverend Mother Gaius Helen Mohiam* in *Dune*
8. “Survival is the ability to swim in strange water.” – *Paul Atreides* in *Dune*
9. “A creature who has developed in a one-sided way may be splendid in that way, but if its strength is turned into a weakness, it is helpless.” – *Frank Herbert* in *Dune*
10. “The mind can go either direction under stress—toward positive or toward negative: on or off. Think of it as a spectrum whose extremes are unconsciousness at the negative end and hyperconsciousness at the positive end. The way the mind will lean under stress is strongly influenced by training.” – *Bene Gesserit* teaching in *Dune*